

The legume choice determines crop production, nitrogen dynamics, weed control and economic viability of relay intercropping in a Mediterranean cereal based low-input cropping system

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Introduction

The relay intercropping of subsidiary legumes with durum wheat (living mulch) can be a valuable agroecological practice to support nutrient availability and non-chemical weed control at crop rotation level without negative impacts on crop productivity (Tosti et al., 2016; Hiltbrunner et al., 2007). This study aimed to investigate the long-term agronomical and economical sustainability of eight different legumes among perennial, annual and annual self-seeding species tested in relay intercropping with durum wheat in a Mediterranean low-input cereal-based cropping system. In particular we evaluated the impact of each legume on 1) intercropped wheat, through the evaluation of N uptake, grain yield and protein content, 2) the subsequent forage sorghum taking into account the residual effects of the legumes on the following summer crop through the evaluation of biomass production and N uptake, 3) the effects of legume on weeds community composition and biomass before and after wheat harvest and in the subsequent cash crop. Finally we performed an economic assessment to test if costs due to the relay intercropping are balanced by the ecosystem services it provides at crop rotation level taking into account the impact of the legumes on the co-cultivated wheat and on the following forage sorghum.

Materials and Methods

A two-year wheat-sorghum rotation was repeated twice at the Centre for Agri-Environmental Research "Enrico Avanzi" of the University of Pisa (Italy). Durum wheat was sown in 18 cm spaced-rows at a rate of 350 viable seeds m⁻² on fields previously ploughed at 25 cm depth and refined with rotary harrow. Legumes used in this experiment include *Medicago sativa*, *Trifolium repens*, *Hedysarum coronarium*, *Medicago lupulina*, *Trifolium incarnatum*, *Trifolium resupinatum*, *Trifolium subterraneum* and *Medicago polymorpha*. Legumes were seeded before the wheat elongation phase in the wheat inter-row space. A control treatment was also implemented with wheat grown as the sole crop to evaluate the incidence of undersown legumes on wheat yield performance. Each treatment was repeated in four randomized blocks. Durum wheat was mechanically harvested. After wheat harvest, legumes persisted in the field during the summer as dead mulch (annual and self-reseeding legumes) or working as cover crops (perennial legumes). In the autumn, self-seeding legumes re-germinated from the seeds disseminated in summer and behaved as cover crops until the sowing of the following crop. Legume biomass was incorporated into the soil in spring and sorghum for forage production was sown at a rate of 150 viable seeds m⁻² in 30 cm wide inter-rows following the legume plots. In the control, after the wheat harvest bare soil with spontaneous vegetation was maintained until the sorghum sowing.

Results

Wheat grain production was on average 3.2 t/ha. Living mulches did not have any negative effects on the durum wheat yield compared with the control for any of the species used in this experiment. We hypothesized instead a beneficial effects of undersown legumes on wheat in terms of N uptake and grain protein content. However, results of this study showed that relay establishment of living mulches had no significant effect on wheat grain yield and quality, but only on the subsequent forage sorghum. The quantity of N accumulated in wheat straw was 48,5 kg N/ha on average and grain protein content was

Figure 1 Legume biomass at spring (dark grey bars) and subsequent sorghum biomass at harvest time (early grey bars) during the second repetition of the experiment

sorghum was sown.

Nitrogen inputs from legumes was estimated by the determination of the nitrogen content in the legume biomass before their termination and incorporation into the soil in spring. Nitrogen input from legume residues vary considerably according to the legume species and seasonal conditions and it ranged from 1.22 to 182 kg/ha. Nitrogen provided by legumes was not totally available for the subsequent crop and sorghum nitrogen uptake ranged from 0.9 to 138 kg/ha. During both repetitions of the experiment *H. coronarium* and *T. repens* and *T. subterraneum* had the highest level of nitrogen content compared with the other legume species. In particular nitrogen input from these legumes was respectively up to 182, 157 and 113 kg/ha. Sorghum dry biomass production in the control plot was on average 4 t/ha. Without the use of external nitrogen, biomass production of sorghum preceded by *H. coronarium*, *T. subterraneum*, *T. repens* and *M. sativa* was 11 t/ha on average (Figure 1), in line with the productive level of the same sorghum grown under conventional conditions. In sorghum, the effect of legume residues mainly affected dicotyledonous weeds whereas residues of *T. resupinatum* and *T. incarnatum* promoted monocotyledonous weeds growth. The economic assessment conducted in this study reveals that relay intercropping reduces profitability of the co-cultivated durum wheat due to the cost for inter-seeding. Instead, the gross income of sorghum (production value – costs) preceded by *H. coronarium*, *T. repens*, *T. subterraneum* and *M. sativa* was up to 955 €/ha. Overall, the use of *H. coronarium* maximised the cumulative gross income (wheat+sorghum) in this cereal-based low-input crop rotation (1381 vs 639.5 €/ha in the control).

Conclusions

Our study highlights the importance of the selection of suitable legumes for relay intercropping with wheat to support nutrient availability and weed control at crop rotation level. Relay establishment of legume living mulches proved to be a viable option to limit the competition with wheat and maintain adequate levels of grain production. However, relay intercropping with legumes did not affect N uptake and grain protein content in wheat. On the other hand a positive effect on the subsequent cash crop was demonstrated. According to the overall agronomic and economic evaluation of legumes throughout the entire growth cycle, *H. coronarium* was identified as the most suitable legume species to be used in relay intercropping with durum wheat in low-input Mediterranean cereal-based cropping system.

Literature

- Tosti et al. 2016. Nitrogen Fertilization Strategies for Organic Wheat Production: Crop Yield and Nitrate Leaching. Ital. J. Agron., 108:770–781.
- Hiltbrunner et al. 2007. Legume cover crops as living mulches for winter wheat: Components of biomass and the control of weeds. Eur. J. of Agron., 26: 21–29.

14,5%. Relay intercropping of legumes proved to be an effective solution to control weeds before and after the wheat harvest, provided suitable legumes species are chosen. Legumes such as *H. coronarium*, *M. sativa*, *T. repens* and *T. subterraneum* reduced the weed biomass up to the 90% during the intercropping (e.g. *M. sativa* 2.03 ± 0.57 vs 23.47 ± 6.60 g/m² weed dry biomass) and up to 96% in the following spring (e.g. *H. coronarium* 8.81 ± 2.15 vs 223.21 ± 53.6 g/m² weed dry biomass) with respect to the control (wheat sole stand crop). The annual legume *T. resupinatum* reduced weed biomass during the intercropping period however, residues of this legume in the following spring (2017-19 growing season) supported weed growth compared with the control (278 ± 30 vs 129 ± 18 g/m² weed dry biomass). Legumes were maintained after wheat harvest and then used as green manure by plowing them under in the following spring when forage